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to Direct Current

Deliverable D6.1

Dissemination and Communication Plan

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Disclaimer

This document has been produced in the context of the Shift2DC project. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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Executive Summary

The Deliverable *Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan* (D6.1) outlines Shift2DC's communication strategy and activities. It consists of at least two versions, being the first submitted at M6 then updated at M24 (or earlier if changes are justified). This deliverable has been prepared by the leader of Work Package WP6 – INESC ID.

The Shift2DC project introduces a new approach on the way direct current (DC) solutions are used in power systems by creating smarter, more efficient, and eco-friendly energy systems. Focusing on the integration of DC solutions in four main infrastructures – Datacentres, Ports, Buildings, and Industry – Shift2DC expects to reshape the way we use electricity.

To become a successful and impactful project, the developed strategies and solutions must be communicated and disseminated to relevant target groups, throughout the project lifespan and beyond. To achieve this purpose, the D&C Plan will primarily specify the key target audiences already identified in the Project proposal and then outline the communication and dissemination strategy, designed to disclose the project main goals and results.

This deliverable follows a preliminary dissemination and communication plan, agreed by the consortium, and presented in Shift2DC grant agreement, now in more detail. Thus, this document presents an overview of Shift2DC target audiences and key messages and offers a look into the project communication channels and tools, highlighting the work developed during the first semester of the project namely in building the project visual identity (logo and its various versions, brand guidelines), developing the related brand materials (templates, headers, flyer and roll ups etc.), launching its online presence (website and social media channels), and planning the initial dissemination activities.

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Keywords, Acronym

AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
WP	Work Package
WG	Working Group
PO	Project Officer
PR	Press Release
R&I	Research and Innovation
SEO	Search-Engine Optimization (SEO)

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and Objectives

The document “D6.1. Dissemination and communication Plan”, corresponds to the first D&C Deliverable of the Shift2DC developed in the Work Package 6 (WP6). This work package focuses on maximizing the impact of the project at a regional, national, and international level, including activities for dissemination of knowledge, networking, and raising awareness of the R&I potential and achievements led under the scope of the project.

To ensure that Shift2DC project achieves its goals and has a meaningful impact, it is crucial to establish and implement communication strategies to widely diffuse the project’s advancements to target audiences, ensuring that the developed solutions and tools are exploited to their full potential.

According to Horizon Europe Work Programme [1], communication is the act of informing the target audiences about the vision, goals, activities, and results of the project; and dissemination is the act of making the research and scientific and technological knowledge available to potential users, being strongly relied on the principle of open science.

Under the scope of this plan, both will work interdependently and together, to maximize the impact of Shift2DC results.

According to the Grant Agreement, the **Shift2DC D&C main strategic goals are:**

- **Ensure maximum visibility** of the project among the target audiences (Figure 2-1) through appropriate key messages and channels,
- **Engage with targeted audiences** to get feedback and validate the project’s results,
- **Maximize the project impact** by making the research, scientific and technological knowledge generated in the SHIF2DC project available within and beyond the project’s consortium,
- **Promote knowledge and innovation transfer by establishing networks** with other projects and initiatives,
- **Attract potential users** and stimulate the appropriate market segment to support the project’s exploitation strategy,
- **Encourage additional outcomes** through the involvement in new initiatives.

Throughout all Shift2DC D&C activities, the purpose is to disclose the benefits of DC solutions to the public and raise awareness about its impact on energy transition, highlighting the role that DC technology can play in achieving EU clean/sustainable energy goals. This D&C plan will support and enhance the potential of the main solutions and results obtained under the SHIF2DC project.

The implementation of these activities will actively involve consortium partners and key stakeholders throughout the various phases of the project, strongly relying on their commitment to carry out the actions described in this deliverable. Due to the multidisciplinary of the consortium, 21 partners and 5 affiliated partners in 13 Countries, Shift2DC is in a great position to reach a multitude of audiences and influence decisions, behaviours, and strategies towards DC solutions adoption.

In addition, most Shift2DC partners have well established networks in specific fields and will be key in reaching out to specific target groups. Therefore, all partners should be committed to carry out the proposed activities to influence relevant audiences.

Under the Grant proposal, the different phases of the dissemination approach have been defined and are outline in Figure 1-1. Each phase will target a different audience and be tailored according to the dissemination objectives, channels, and tools. The plan will be refined and updated throughout the project life cycle to reflect the project's progress and new opportunities considered.

The dissemination activities will continue after the end of the project to guarantee sustainability of results and impact of the project.

Figure 1-1 - Shift2DC Dissemination approach.

All D&C activities must be communicated to the Shift2DC Coordination Team, responsible for leading, managing and keeping a record of all WP6 actions. The initial identification of the SHIFT2DC target groups, as well as the dissemination and communication activities, are summarized below.

1.2 Structure

The current document is divided into six sections plus two annexes. Section 1 introduces and describes the deliverable. Section 2 presents the Shift2DC target audiences and respective key messages. Section 3 describes the communication channels and tools. Section 4 identifies the dissemination activities. Section 5 describes how to evaluate and monitor communication and dissemination activities. Section 6 presents overall conclusions and considerations about this deliverable. Finally, [ANNEX I](#) and [ANNEX II](#) sections show the standard brand guidelines and the Shift2DC power point template, respectively.

1.3 Relationship with other deliverables

Deliverable 6.1 establishes the plan of D&C, focusing on Shift2DC activities, events, and results held throughout the project. This document defines the strategies to be followed to ensure that the knowledge and results produced within the project are properly communicated and disseminated to the identified target groups.

This deliverable is transversal to all activities executed within all WPs of the project, in particular to those related to the demonstration sites. The main D&C activities are managed by the WP6 Coordination team at INESC ID and will be further detailed in this document. However, it is essential to foster the engagement and participation of all WP and task leaders, to support the disclosure of the D&C activities. An updated plan will be submitted at M24 (Deliverable D6.2), or earlier if changes are applied.

2 Target Audiences

The **Shift to Direct Current (Shift2DC) project** introduces a new approach on the way DC solutions are used in our power systems by creating smarter, more efficient, and eco-friendly energy systems. Focusing on the integration of DC solutions in four main infrastructures – Data Centre, Buildings, Industry and Ports – Shift2DC expects to reshape the way we use electricity.

To do so, the consortium will establish comprehensive guidelines and a roadmap for the widespread application of DC in diverse energy scenarios to develop, test and demonstrate the technical feasibility, cost-benefit, life cycle and environmental impact of the proposed DC solutions in four demonstration sites: two across Germany (Data Centre and Industry), one in France (Building), and one in Portugal (Port) to test medium voltage DC (MVDC) and low voltage DC (LVDC) solutions.

For a successful implementation of the project, it is crucial to inform citizens, industries, academia, and governments about the Shift2DC vision, strategies, and solutions. To achieve that, the project will count on the involvement of partners and on the Demos leaders to support this D&C Plan.

Furthermore, Shift2DC is also expected to have a broad impact across Europe and worldwide in the power and energy sectors. The project expects to test and demonstrate DC solutions, evaluate users' perspective regarding DC solutions and finally propose new tools that promote the faster adoption of DC solutions.

Thus, our communication strategies will be developed at **two levels**:

- **Local/National-targeted communication**, with a special focus on the 13 countries where the project has partners, on the countries that are hosting the 4 Demo sites (Portugal, Germany, and France) and where the two Living Labs will be implemented (Germany and Spain).

The local/national communication initiatives, such as the participation or organization of events and workshops, will target local and national citizens, end users, national businesses and industries, municipalities, and governments, to ensure their engagement and interest in the project activities throughout the project. Countries where the Demonstrators or where the Living Labs will be implemented have additional opportunities for dissemination and communication Table 1.

Local and national awareness will expand the Shift2DC network, foster new opportunities and create local value. The project will promote, as a general key message, that Shift2DC will present more efficient, greener, and cost-effective DC solutions, compared to traditional AC ones. The efforts described next in Table 1 will increase the Shift2DC impact on local communities, cities, and countries.

Table 1 - Local/National D&C Activities

	Key message	Communication Activities	Dissemination Activities
All Consortium Countries/Partners	Raise awareness about the project, goals, and solutions. Disclose to National audiences the Institution /Country Role under the project and expected Outcomes	Disclose information about the project on Institutional Channels: website, social media, newsletters. Publications in National media, such as interviews and opinion articles, press releases (PRs) Participation in Outreach events	Participation in conferences, fairs, and other events to present the project to Local/National audiences.
Countries with Demo Sites	Enhance public opinion and foster the discussion on DC by showing Shift2DC strategies and solutions that are being developed and tested onsite.	Promote a Media coverage with a national media newspaper or other relevant media on each Demo location to share what is being implemented. Share photos and videos on social media with Updates on the Demo Activities	Organize at least one workshop per Demo site to engage with Local and National Communities.
Living Labs	Inform about SHIFT2DC solutions, tools, methodologies highlighting what is being developed in the two Living Labs. Draw the attention to the advantages of adopting DC technology.	Promote media coverage with a national media newspaper or other relevant media to share what is being implemented in the two Living Labs. Share photos and videos on social media with regular updates.	Organize visits in Spain and Germany to the two Living Labs with relevant stakeholders (industry, scientific communities, municipalities and authorities etc..)

Support materials for local/national communication: although all materials developed in the context of Shift2DC will be written in English, communication materials such as flyers, rollups, newsletters, and videos, can also be adapted into the partners own languages and made available on the Shift2DC website, shared among social media, and distributed at local events and conferences to reach local communities more efficiently.

- **European/international-targeted communication, directed to European institutions** (e.g., European Commission), **European and worldwide countries and global energy markets.**

Shift2DC communication will also target citizens, the energy sector, and policymakers in Europe and Worldwide, to promote important synergies and knowledge transfer. As a general key message will be reinforced that Shift2DC will provide new services, solutions and business models offering effective solutions for the widespread application of DC in diverse energy scenarios.

Strategies for International communication: as mentioned before, all materials developed in the context of Shift2DC will be primarily in English to reach a global audience. Shift2DC partners will also, whenever possible, participate in international conferences, Liaison events and other initiatives namely communication activities such as press releases or other media articles, on international newspapers and magazines. Results generated in the context of the project will be published in peer-review international journals, increasing the international visibility and impact of the project.

Strategies for Joint Collaboration with other peer projects: Shift2DC will work to identify possible collaboration networks with Horizon Europe peer projects. To achieve this goal, the project will try to assess available communication channels, collaboration platforms and eventually organize cluster meetings. INESC ID Coordination will evaluate the possibility of creating cross-project working groups and leveraging joint workshops and events to facilitate knowledge exchange and networking opportunities. Analysing and defining joint strategies can be key for maximizing the impact of collaboration and achieving shared goals.

For the D&C activities to be effective and successful, it is crucial to identify tailored and customized messages according to each target audience and their needs. Several target audiences have already been identified before the start of the project and are now presented in Section 2.1 Section 2.2. will focus on specific Key Messages and Channels defined according to each Target Audience.

2.1 Identification of Target Audiences

To ensure that the Shift2DC project achieves its key objectives, the project has identified key messages according to specific target audiences to ensure that the developed solutions and tools are exploited to their full potential.

The Shift2DC vision, goals and results will be disseminated across several target groups (Figure 2-1). Since the project is in its initial phase, this list might undergo some changes to adapt to the Shift2DC strategies and solutions that will be developed.

Figure 2-1 - Shift2DC Target Groups

One of the main target groups of the Shift2DC project comprises Citizens, Media, and End Users, to spread information about the project. First the project will focus on disclosing its goals and strategy, and in a more advanced stage on its results and achievements. This implies involving the non-scientific public and end-users in the debate, engaging the community on issues related to the project, such as the role of DC, the developed solutions, its environmental impact, and general contributions.

The D&C plan will also target more specific audiences that are further detailed in the next section, focusing on the stakeholders that may use or benefit directly from the research results in their own activities and work – such as the scientific community, policy makers or industry partners.

2.2 Key Messages and Channels by Target Audience

The tables below (Table 2, Table 3, Table 4, Table 5) shows key messages and channels according to the four main target groups identified for the Shift2DC project. As mentioned before, due to the multidisciplinary nature of the consortium, specific partners will reach specific target groups easier than others, according to their expertise and network. Thus, the consortium will be committed to assure effective communication to all identified audiences.

Table 2 - Target audience: Citizens, Media, and end Users - Key messages and channels

Audiences	Key message	Activities	Communication tools
Citizens	Raise awareness about the project strategies, goals and solutions. Place DC as an effective alternative to Alternating Current (AC).	Workshops, events	Website, social media, publications in media, press releases (PRs), newsletters, videos, rollups, flyers
Media	Enhance public opinion via Media channels, to support the discussion on DC and support Shift2DC strategies and solutions.	Outreach Events	PRs and other media activities (opinion articles, interviews)
End Users	Inform about Shift2DC solutions, tools, methodologies highlighting the benefits of DC and empower them on energy transition. Draw the attention to the advantages of adopting DC technology.	Workshop, events	Website, social media, newsletter, videos, rollups

Table 3 - Target audience: Policy Makers, Regular Entities and Authorities - Key messages and channels

Audiences	Key message	Activities	Communication tools
Policy Makers	Shift2DC will create new business models and propose regulatory frameworks for different countries based on demonstrators. Highlight the role that DC can play in achieving EU clean/sustainable energy goals.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, videos, newsletters, social media, flyers
Regular Entities	Shift2DC will create business ecosystems, and influence policy priorities and the results generated will attract more public funding opportunities.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, publications in media, newsletter, videos, rollups
Authorities: European Institutions	The Shift2DC impactful results will attract more public funding opportunities and recommend new policies.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, publications in media, newsletters, videos, rollups, posters

Table 4 - Target audience: Industry and Scientific Communities - Key messages and channels

Audiences	Key message	Activities
Energy-related Industry	Shift2DC will provide new services, solutions and business models offering effective solutions for the widespread application of DC in diverse energy scenarios.	Workshops, events, scientific publications, conferences
Scientific communities Universities and R&I Centres	Shift2DC will provide results from the demonstration activities and up-to-date knowledge from the lessons learned in the demonstration sites	Workshops, events, scientific publications, conferences
Scientific communities: European Research projects	Shift2DC will create new opportunities for synergies with other European projects (Bridge Working Groups, Clusters with peer projects etc..)	Liaison events, scientific publications, conferences

Table 5 - Target audience: Services and Technology Providers - Key messages and channels

Audiences	Key message	Activities	Communication tools
Services	Shift2DC will provide new services, solutions and business models offering effective Solutions for the widespread application of DC in diverse energy scenarios.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, newsletter, videos, rollups, flyers
Technology Providers	Shift2DC will develop and test DC solutions and strategies at 4 different demonstration sites.	Workshops, events, conferences	Website, social media, publications in media, newsletter, videos, rollups, flyers

3 Communication Channels and Tools

The communication channels and tools proposed in the current D&C Plan, aim to increase the project visibility, recognition, and awareness and to promote active engagement with the target audiences.

In the next sub-sections, will be presented an overview of all the communication tools and channels: Shift2DC Visual identity and Tools (Section 3.1), Website (Section 3.2), social media (Section 3.3), Newsletters (Section 3.4), Promotional materials (Section 3.5), Media Activities (Section 3.6) and Videos (Section 3.7).

3.1 Shift2DC Visual Identity and Tools

Together with a professional design agency, a project visual identity was developed and will be consistently applied in all the Shift2DC channels, promotional materials, and tools, including:

- Website and social media channels;
- Branded stationery (letterhead paper, email signature, web call background, folders, etc.);
- Project official templates (Word; PowerPoint);
- Communication toolkit (flyers, project presentation, posters);
- Videos.

This section presents the logo (Section 3.1.1), colour palette (Section 3.1.2), and brand guidelines (Section 3.1.3). The materials here presented are available to all Shift2DC partners via Shift2DC internal SharePoint.

3.1.1 Shift2DC Logo and Rationale

The logotype is the main visual support of the project, and must be present in all communication tools, channels, and materials. A preliminary version of the Shift2DC was developed by the INESC ID team and submitted in the Grant Agreement. This initial version was then renewed and improved by a professional design team in the first month of the project. The final version of the logo was approved in the second Scientific Committee meeting. The final vertical and horizontal colour versions are presented in Figure 3-2 and the logos adapted to different backgrounds in Figure 3-3.

The design of the logo comprises the project acronym split in two parts using two distinct colours “Shift” (green) - 2DC (blue), representing the main concept of the Project (Figure 3-1), that is to shift from traditional AC solutions to DC Solutions. Both text elements are connected to graphic elements: “Shift” is coupled to a sinusoidal wave that represents AC power, and “2DC” to a straight-line representing DC or direct current, a current with zero frequency and no oscillation.

The primary colours of the project are green and blue: green represents the environment, efficiency, and sustainability and blue represents Europe, the planet, and innovation. Both the logo and other materials (e.g., Powerpoint template and banners) are both colours.

All elements combined represent the concept and vision of the project: develop solutions to shift from AC to DC shown in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1 - Shift2DC concept

The logo was designed to be used across multiple platforms (website tabs, apps, social media) and different backgrounds. When the logo is displayed on a blue or green background, the logo should be used in one colour, white. When presented on a white or black background, the logo should be presented with a gradient of green and blue. It is also possible to display a one-colour black logo on a lighter grey background as shown in Figure 3-3. The logo has a minimum size as shown in Figure 3-2.

Dimensions

HORIZONTAL

SMALLEST SIZE

VERTICAL

SMALLEST SIZE

Figure 3-2 - Shift2DC colour logos (horizontal and vertical) and Dimensions

Backgrounds

Figure 3-3 - Shift2DC logos in different Backgrounds

Figure 3-4 - Shift2DC tagline

3.1.2 Colour Palette

Shift2DC main colours, derivations and secondary colours are shown in Figure 3-5. The primary colours are green and blue, with green representing as mentioned above, the environment, efficiency, and sustainability and Blue representing Europe and the European Union, the planet, and innovation.

Figure 3-5 - Shift2DC colour palette.

3.1.3 Demonstrator icons

The Shift2DC project will be tested in four demonstrators – Data Centre, Buildings, Industry, and Ports - that will be installed in three European countries: Germany, France and Portugal. To represent each one of the Demonstrators, four image icons were developed by the design team. These icons are graphical representations of each demo type and will be used to illustrate and support all visual tools and materials related to the demonstrators (Figure 3-6).

Figure 3-6 - Demos Icons

3.1.4 Shift2DC Templates

Within the project several templates have been developed with the Shift2DC visual identity described above, to ensure a coherent and professional visual identity in the materials used by all consortia partners. All templates are available in a dedicated folder in Shift2DC's internal SharePoint.

The available templates so far include Word-format templates (*Deliverables, Internal reports, Meeting agenda, Meeting minutes, Meeting list of Attendance* and soon will be added also the *Newsletter template*), and a

PowerPoint template that has been developed by the design agency to be used by all partners for internal and external presentations (e.g., conferences, consortium meetings, public outreach, presented in (ANNEX II).

If partners develop a non-existing template for their needs, they should also upload it to the Shift2DC internal SharePoint folder so that it can also be used by other partners, if needed.

All templates shall contain the Shift2DC logo, graphic elements of the project (ANNEX I) and the European Commission flag with the following disclaimer, acknowledging the EU funding: *“Funded by European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101136131. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.*

3.2 Shift2DC Website

The project website will be the main media hub for dissemination of Shift2DC initiatives and serve as a repository of all the project activities during the project lifecycle and beyond. **The Shift2DC public website domain is:** <https://shift2dc.eu/> and was launched at the beginning of M6 (May of 2024). **Language:** English.

The website structure was planned to allow easy access to information and navigation, organizing the existing content in a coherent and intuitive way. Attention was paid to implement a clear and consistent design and navigation system that helps users easily find what they're looking for: a menu bar with easily recognizable labels and submenus for more detailed categories.

The website will target all audiences identified earlier (Section 2) and aims to promote interactions with other initiatives, projects, and working groups to increase public awareness and engagement.

Website structure:

The website features a simple, modern and accessible design using the Shift2DC brand identity. The website has a responsive design to ensure that it is accessible and usable across different devices and screen sizes (smartphones, tablets, laptops).

The overall goal was to create a website that is easy to navigate with clear contents and cross-platform support. A brief description of the website content and structure follows.

Homepage:

The homepage header (Figure 3-7) consists of an animated image that reflects the project main vision and the concept behind the Logotype (Section 3.1.1). The animation starts with a sinusoidal wave that represents AC power, moves, and goes through the project logotype. When passing the Logo, the curve becomes a zero frequency DC line that passes through the project icons symbolizing the four demonstrators: Data Centre, Buildings, Industry and Ports.

Figure 3-7 - Website Header and main Menu

The Homepage includes the Shift2DC logo, a section “in brief” or “in numbers” with facts about the project (duration of the project, number of partners and countries involved, number of demonstration sites and use cases, and funding), a text box with the Shift2DC vision, a section with the latest news and next event, logos and names of the consortium partners, and a footer with links to Shift2DC social media (X/Twitter and LinkedIn), link for CORDIS website, and European Commission logo and disclaimer. (Figure 3-8).

HOME ABOUT RESEARCH & INNOVATION MEDIA & EVENTS CONTACTS

Revolutionizing the way we use electricity.

📅 42 months

📅 December 2023 to June 2027

👥 21 partners + 6 affiliated

🌍 13 Countries

🏢 4 DEMOS

💶 11 M€ EU Funding

SHIFT2DC VISION

The Shift2DC Horizon Europe introduces a new approach on the way direct current (DC) solutions are used in power systems by creating smarter, more efficient, and eco-friendly energy systems. Focusing on the integration of DC solutions in four main infrastructures - Datacenters, Ports, Buildings, and industry - Shift2DC expects to reshape the way we use electricity.

[READ MORE](#)

COORDINATOR

CONSORTIUM

DC FOUNDATIONS

ASSOCIATED PARTNERS

NEWS

SHIFT2DC Meeting with EHPA
Associates a discussion to explore the potential of DC Solutions to Heat pumps.

On April 23rd, the Shift2DC project hosted an online meeting in collaboration with the European Heat Pump Association (EHPA), one of the project partner institutions, to discuss strategies concerning Direct Current (DC) solutions and to explore the potential for future collaborations between EHPA's associates and Shift2DC consortium members.

[Read more](#)

SHIFT2DC partners meet in Madeira to discuss the next steps of the Portuguese Demo

On April 3rd, Shift2DC partners involved in the Portuguese demonstrator were gathered to discuss the next steps of the Demo based in Funchal, Madeira (Portugal).

[Read more](#)

SHIFT2DC at the BRIDGE General Assembly

This year's edition of the 2024 Bridge General Assembly (GA) was held in Brussels on April 9 and 10.

[Read more](#)

[ALL NEWS](#)

UPCOMING EVENTS

MAY 16

JRP DC GRIDS FINAL WORKSHOP

On May 16th the Shift2DC Project will be part of the DC Grids project, Final Project Workshop "Standardisation of Measurements for DC Electricity Grids", in the Netherlands.

[GO TO EVENT](#)

JUNE 12 - 13

SHIFT2DC GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The Shift2DC General Assembly will take place in Aachen, Germany hosted by RWTH Aachen University.

[GO TO EVENT](#)

JUNE 24 - 28

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION SUMMIT

Between June 24 and 28 will take place in Madeira the Digital Transformation Summit and Shift2DC will be part in the Workshop "5G - Smart, Efficient and Sustainable Energy Use".

[GO TO EVENT](#)

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SEARCH

Figure 3-8 - Website Homepage

The website Menu is divided in four main Tabs, to allow a more intuitive and easy navigation through all the contents. Next is a brief description of each sub-menu: About, Research & Innovation, Media & Events and Contacts.

About:

The About section is split in **three sub-sections**:

- **Overview and Mission:** with essential information about the project, its mission, goals, and objectives.
- **Consortium:** with information about the Consortium partners. This page includes a European map with partners distributed according to their Home Country, and identified by an icon that represents their area of activity (Research Centre/University, Utility, Technology Provider, Foundation/Association, and Industry). Under the Map are listed the partner Logos with a click button that leads to an individual page for each partner that will include: a Description of the Institution, Role within the Project and link to their website and social media Channels.
- **Work Packages (WP):** with information about each WP. By clicking on each WP tab, one can see the description and the Lead partner.

Research & Innovation:

The Shift2DC R&I Section provides an overview of the Research activities planned for each Demonstration site and to keep a record of the main resources of the project: scientific publications and public deliverables.

This section is divided into **three sub-sections** for an easy access to information:

- **Demos:** the Demonstrators page provides more detailed information about the Demo sites. By clicking on each Demo icon, one can see the objectives, use cases that will be tested in each demo and images of the sites. This information was reviewed by the partners involved.
- **Deliverables:** will provide access to all project Deliverables.
- **Publications:** will list all project Publications (Journal Papers, Conference Papers, Posters and Presentations at Conferences).

Media & Events:

The Media & Events section includes all the announcements of activities related to the communication and dissemination of the project including news, information about events, Newsletters, and brand materials for Download.

This section is divided in **four sub-sections**:

- **News:** to disclose all the information about Shift2DC latest activities and initiatives, the communication team will regularly produce and share news articles for the website.
- **Events:** to announce all future events related to the Project

- **Newsletters:** to provide access and allow the download of the Project Newsletters, plus display a newsletter subscription form.
- **Logo & Promotional Materials:** to share the project Logos and promotional materials for consultation and/or download (Logotype, Brand Guidelines, flyers, etc.)

Contacts:

The Contact Us page (Figure 3-9) provides a form requiring name, email, subject and message. The form is linked to the shit2dc.dissemination@inesc-id.pt mailing list and the Shift2DC coordination team at INESC ID will receive and reply to all messages. The data collected will be stored during the project and deleted at the end of it. This page also provides information about the Coordination Institution contacts and how to connect on social media.

Figure 3-9 - Contacts Page

3.2.1 Technical Development and Management

The Shift2DC website was developed by a design agency using [WordPress](#), an open-source content management software and [GoDaddy](#), that provides services related to domain registration, website hosting, website building, and online marketing.

INESC ID, the task leader, will be responsible for the management of the website and content update, with the contribution of all partners. The website will be maintained for at least 5 years, which means that it will remain alive for 2 years after the end of the project.

3.2.2 Search-Engine Optimization (SEO) and Analytics

The website will be Search-Engine optimization-friendly to improve its visibility to search engines such as Google, and Yahoo, among others. INESC ID will be responsible for analysing the website traffic through google analytics, collecting data on the number of visitors, average duration of visits, number of page views, and number of references to the project on search engines.

This data will be used to monitor the visibility of the website and, when necessary, to plan strategies to increase its popularity. This information will be collected for the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) checks throughout the project.

3.3 Shift2DC Social Media

In addition to the project's website, Shift2DC will be strongly focused on other online activities namely on social media channels (LinkedIn and X/Twitter).

The use of web-based platforms is increasingly widespread amongst individuals and organizations giving the opportunity to establish dialogue, build relationships and engage with broader audiences. The Project's main goal is to establish and increase its audience through an active online engagement at these selected platforms.

The social media presence will be strengthened by leveraging extensive networks of project partners to build the Shift2DC social media presence. To generate engagement from specific stakeholders or on specific topics hashtags will be strategically used (e.g., #Shift2DC, #DCResearch #EnergyTransition #MVDC #LVDC, handles (e.g., @HorizonEU, @DigitalEU, @Cinea @Shift2DC.) and partners handles whenever relevant.

Shift2DC social media channels will be used to communicate the latest news of the project including publications, newsletters, participation and/or organization of events, to announce events, inform about activities at demonstration sites, present Shift2DC partners and their achievements, and to engage with other projects and activities. The efforts on social media channels are expected to increase target audiences' interest in the project, engage in activities and events organized by the Shift2DC consortium, encourage them to keep up with the project outputs and download them from the website, and ultimately incorporate the Shift2DC solutions and strategies developed.

All Shift2DC partners are expected to provide content and actively promote these social media channels by *sharing, liking, and commenting on* its publications.

All these accounts are maintained in English, to be accessible to all audiences. All Shift2DC social media channels are public and will be maintained/administrated throughout the project by INESC ID, the WP6 leader.

Common strategies will be followed on the different social media channels to increase visibility and the number of interactions and followers:

- minimum of one publication per week.
- monthly assessment of social media data analytics to monitor the engagement with the public and plan, when necessary, strategies to improve its visibility. These data will also be collected for the KPIs checks (Section 5);
- all publications will follow, consistently, the visual identity developed for Shift2DC;
- our publications will identify using @ whenever relevant, involved partners and stakeholders to engage them to repost our content on their Institutional channels;
- the majority of publications will contain videos and images to increase engagement with the audience;
- all social media channels will be referred in the Shift2DC project website and mentioned/promoted in dissemination materials and project presentations.

Additionally, to keep the engagement and guarantee a regular publications flow, specific Shift2DC Social Media Campaigns will be implemented as described next.

Shift2DC Social Media Campaigns:

To present and introduce the Shift2DC large consortium, the plan is to prepare a regular post with information about each partner and a quote with their role under the project, as shown in Figure 3-10.

Figure 3-10 - Social Media Partners Post

In addition, periodic posts called “Do you know that...” will share information about DC solutions and its benefits, as shown in Figure 3-11.

Figure 3-11 - Social media “Do you know that?” Post

Once the demonstration activities start, and with the help of the partners involved, the plan is to regularly upload photos and developments on social media. Additionally, specific campaigns will mark Celebration Days as for example the EU Energy Day or World Energy Day.

3.3.1 Shift2DC LinkedIn

Shift2DC LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/101348716>) has been active since M1 (December 2023).

A banner was designed for the LinkedIn Header using Shift2DC’s graphic elements, logo, and tagline (Figure 3-12). The LinkedIn homepage includes an overview of the project and provides a link to the Shift2DC project website. Due to the nature of this channel (no limit on characters), more detailed information (than the one provided on X/Twitter) can be provided regarding Shift2DC outputs, events, and activities.

As of May 20th, 2024, 6 months after Shift2DC LinkedIn account launch, the channel had reached the 581 followers’ milestone (initial target was 200 followers). These numbers are promising, and the expectation is to have built by the end of the project a much larger network of professionals covering the energy value chain. With this purpose, the Coordination team will keep the account regularly updated and share relevant content for its stakeholders. INESC ID will count on the Shift2DC consortium to join, share, and comment on the posts. With this effort, the project will reach a large community of interested stakeholders and potential users, ensuring knowledge transfer and dissemination.

Figure 3-12 - Shift2DC LinkedIn account

3.3.2 Shift2DC X/Twitter

Shift2DC X/Twitter account: @Shift2DC_2023, https://x.com/Shift2DC_2023, has been active since M4.

Hashtags: #SHIFT2DC #DC #DCResearch #HorizonEu #HorizonEurope #Innovation #DigitalEu #EnergyTransition #MVDC #LVDC #Sustainability

The Social Media header was also adapted for the X/Twitter account using Shift2DC’s graphic elements, logo, and tagline (Figure 3-13).

Due to the nature of this social media channel, Shift2DC posts on X/Twitter will be short (max. 280 characters), concise, and use video clips and animated images whenever possible to inform its audience on the latest project developments, news articles, activities, events, etc, while incorporating relevant hashtags and emojis.

At May 20th, 2024 (two months after Shift2DC X/Twitter release), the account had 41 followers and 18 publications. The goal is to reach a larger number of followers, a minimum of 200. For this purpose, the channel administrator will actively follow and interact (re-tweeting, commenting and liking other tweets) with relevant audiences and will post Shift2DC tweets every week, preferentially more often if there is content to share. The partners are expected to interact with/retweet the Shift2DC posts among their followers.

Figure 3-13 - Shift2DC X/Twitter account

3.4 Shift2DC Newsletters

Shift2DC Consortium will release a trimestral digital newsletter to promote its initiatives, including news, events, and published papers, to be distributed through electronic mail, shared on our social media networks and available on our website. Subscription (and unsubscribe option) to the newsletters will be possible through the Shift2DC website.

Newsletters will have a digital format and be sent via a mailing distribution platform, disclosing information about the project, consortium, activities, news and results, with links to the information on the Project website for further consultation.

Newsletters will include a brief editorial section, written by the project coordinator and other WP Leaders about the status of the project or a relevant topic on DC latest developments, a section about events, a section about the activities of the project, a section about the consortium (including, when applicable, highlights about partners, partner interviews, etc.), a section regarding publications produced in the context of the project, and a section about upcoming events.

Information will also be provided on how to subscribe to future newsletters and the links to the Shift2DC website and social media. All partners are invited to contribute with their content.

The first issue of the newsletter is planned for July 2024 and will first circulate among the Scientific Committee for approval, through the project mailing list. The newsletter will then be sent electronically to subscribed contacts, disseminated via social media channels, and shared on the Newsletters tab of the Shift2DC website.

3.5 Shift2DC Promotional Materials

To support the disclosure of the project at events and other onsite initiatives, a communication toolkit will be developed and updated according to the needs.

In all Shift2DC promotional materials will feature the project Logo and when relevant the tagline “Revolutionizing the way we use electricity”, the visual colours and the graphic elements of the project, that have been described in Section 3.1 and ANNEX I. As previously stated, all materials must include the European flag and the associated disclaimer.

Some Shift2DC materials have already been developed and are available in the internal SharePoint folder: a Shift2DC Flyer and Shift2DC Roll Up (Figure 3-14 and Figure 3-15, respectively). The flyer is an A5 bi-fold brochure with 4 pages, containing information about the vision and goals of the project, demonstration sites, and the consortium. The Roll-up banner (Figure 3-15) has 85x200cm and will be used in exhibitions, events, and conferences.

These materials will be shared among all Shift2DC members and will be available as a pdf file and editable file (Adobe illustrated format), allowing partners to update, translate for their own languages and adapt the material for their needs (specific meetings, conferences). These materials (pdf format) will also be available on the Shift2DC website.

Other materials are expected to be developed throughout the project, according to the needs of the partners and to include specific campaigns, which are essential action towards disseminating and exploiting results. The materials can be developed by any partner following the guidelines above described and should always be shared among all partners and uploaded in the Shift2DC internal SharePoint.

The **SHIFT to Direct Current (SHIFT2DC)** project introduces a new approach on the way direct current (DC) solutions are used in our power systems by creating smarter, more efficient, and eco-friendly energy systems. Focusing on the integration of DC solutions in four main infrastructures – Datacenters, Ports, Buildings, and Industry – Shift2DC expects to reshape the way we use electricity.

Funded by the Horizon Europe research and innovation program, the Project counts on the expertise of 21 partners and 6 affiliated partners from thirteen countries, and is led by the Portuguese Research & Innovation Institute **INESC-ID**.

Throughout the Project 42 months, the consortia will establish comprehensive guidelines and a roadmap for the widespread application of DC solutions in diverse energy scenarios to develop, test and demonstrate the technical feasibility, cost-benefit, life cycle and environmental impact of the proposed DC solutions in four demonstrators: two across Germany (Datacenter and Industry), one in France (Building), and one in Portugal (Port) to test medium voltage DC (MVDC) and Low Voltage DC (LVDC) solutions.

Shift2DC in Numbers

 42 months	 21 partners + 6 affiliated	 December 2023 to June 2027
 13 Countries	 4 Demos	 11 M€ EU Funding

The Four Demonstrators

Buildings

France

The real-life commercial building demonstrator will be developed in France. The planned DC Infrastructure will supply all DC compatible power needs of the building including the connection of PV system, DC/DC EV charging stations, heat pumps, a battery energy storage system as well as the traditional loads.

Data Centre

The Data Centre Demonstrator located at the premises of Bachmann (Germany), will be set up in a container, housing two different compartments both supplied by the same DC distribution grid.

Industry

Germany

The Industry demonstrator will be performed at EATON/RWTH, where MVDC connection and protection systems will be demonstrated, and in PHOENIX, where LVAC/LVDC interface will be tested.

Ports

Madeira, Portugal

The Port Demonstrator will be implemented in Funchal (Madeira Island) and has two main objectives: to study the potential of DC in Ports by leveraging a Digital Twin of the Funchal Port and to analyze user perspectives.

Figure 3-14 - Shift2DC Flyer (bi-fold document)

SHIFT to Direct Current

The Four Demonstrators

Buildings
France

The real-life commercial building demonstrator will be developed in France. The planned DC infrastructure will supply all DC compatible power needs of the building including the connection of PV system, DC/DC EV charging stations, heat pumps, a battery energy storage system as well as the traditional loads.

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The industry demonstrator will be performed at EATON/RWTH, where MVDC connection and protection systems will be demonstrated, and in PHOENIX, where LVAC/LVDC interface will be tested.

Coordinator

Consortium

Funded by the European Union

DC Foundations

Associated Partners

shift2dc.eu

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Figure 3-15- Shift2DC Roll Up Banner

3.6 Shift2DC Media Activities

To disclose the Project initiatives to a broader audience, the Coordination team at INESC ID will work towards enhancing the Project's achievements and initiatives, through specific Media activities.

Shift2DC Press Releases (PR) will be one of the key channels to disclose the project to the media, both at a local, national, and European level. The goal is to generate media press coverage on relevant outcomes and project results. So far, one press release has been released by the Coordination team at INESC ID in Portuguese and English, to disclose the launch of the project.

This Press release was distributed to Portuguese Media via the INESC ID Communications Office and replicated by APRAM (Administration of the Ports of the Autonomous Region of Madeira), mostly in regional media of the Madeira Island. The Press Release was also distributed (English version) through the Alpha Galileo news release platform, available through the INESC Brussels Hub. This news was covered by several media outlets, resulting in 19 news articles (ANNEX III).

Other activities, such as the start of the demo activities and later, their outcomes, may also be of interest to the media. At the end of the project a PR with an overview of the project's achievements will be prepared and sent to National and International Media, via INESC ID. The PR will also be shared among the Consortium Institutions hopefully counting on their support to disclose the information in each of the involved Countries.

Additionally, other activities involving the media can be implemented throughout the project, to disclose the project to a broader audience. This will include negotiating specific articles with journalists to try to promote an interview, opinion article, or other journalistic content to disclose the outcomes of the project, possibly closer to the end of the project when results are available.

All partners are also encouraged to develop press releases and participate in other media activities, to ensure that Shift2DC-related information reaches all target audiences, in all the consortium countries.

When such publications are planned, they must be communicated to the Shift2DC Coordination Team through the dedicated mailing list (shift2dc.coordination@inesc-id.pt). The Coordination Team will keep a database of all publications and will also disclose the content in the news section of the website and social media channels under the tag "In the Media".

3.7 Shift2DC Videos

During the preparation of the proposal, one video was proposed featuring the activities developed at the demonstration sites. Since demo activities will only start at M13, the video will be developed later on, with the support of a professional video production company.

4 Dissemination Activities

In Section 3, was presented the communication tools and channels that will be used to release Shift2DC initiatives and results to a broad audience. Section 4 will go through the dissemination activities that are planned to raise awareness of the project results but, most importantly, to make them public so stakeholders can exploit them for other activities (e.g., research, policymaking, training, among others).

Dissemination activities will be key on supporting the disclosure of DC research to aspiring researchers and reach out to other relevant communities through: publication of scientific research articles and books (Section 4.1), participation in conferences and workshops (Section 4.2), organization of workshops and events (Section 4.3), development of patents and synergies with peer projects (Section 4.4).

The planned actions will ensure that participant partners from research, industry, and academia, in compliance with contractual arrangements, will properly disseminate and efficiently exploit the results generated within the project. Finally, a perspective on the rules on consortium participation within the dissemination activities (Section 4.5).

4.1 Shift2DC Scientific Research Publications

Shift2DC results are aimed to be published in well-established peer-reviewed scientific journals and conference journals. Some examples are the IEEE Transaction on Power Systems, IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids, or the Electric Power Systems Research.

According to Horizon Europe policies (Article 17 of the Grant Agreement)[2], peer-reviewed articles and respective data should be made available through open science in trusted repositories. Thus, once Shift2DC partners submit articles to specialized peer-reviewed journals (giving preference to open science journals), those should be also available in SHIFT2DC website and if possible, in institutional repositories". Some data can also be published in Shift2DC [Zenodo community repository](#).

The Coordination Team at INESC ID has developed a List (available in Sharepoint), outlining all the Work packages and tasks that have the potential to submit publications. A list of Conferences where these publications could be submitted was also listed and shared with the consortium.

All partners should inform the Shift2DC Coordination Team (shift2dc.coordination@inesc-id.pt) about the submitted and accepted publications (Section 4.5). By the end of the project, is expected to have at least 21 scientific articles published among all consortium partners.

4.2 Shift2DC Participation in Events/Conferences

To fulfill the communication and dissemination objectives, project partners will identify key national and international events, ensuring the project involvement in a wide spectrum of initiatives. All consortium partners are encouraged to participate in local or national events such as Open Days, for example promoted by Universities and Research Institutes, or National/European events such as the European Researchers Night, to raise awareness about the project to a broader audience.

On the other end, the project will disseminate new solutions, tools, and technology advancements through specialized conferences (e.g., CIRED- International Conference on Electricity Distribution; SEST - International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies) and other scientific forums, mainly by the academic partners, as well as through the establishment of synergies with peer projects (e.g. BRIDGE initiatives).

Additionally, the project will be presented yearly at The Heat Pump Forum, EHPA's flagship event that brings together high-profile speakers and experts from business communities, universities, Research Centres, EU policymakers, media, and relevant energy stakeholders. The plan also includes regular presentations to EHPA's Heat Pump Manufacturing and EHPA's Research and Innovation Committee. In April 2024, the Coordination office organized a first meeting to present to EHPA associates DC solutions being developed under the project, and by the project partners. This meeting included presentations by: ODCA, CurrentOS and Schneider Electric, Taltech, Fraunhofer, RWTH, JJ Cooling, Hitachi Energy, Watt & Well followed by a 30 minute discussion.

The two leading European associations on DC, CurrentOS and ODCA, will also play an important role in relaying the project achievements to their partners and in open forums. Industry partners will focus on workshops, information days, and internal and external client meetings.

Attendance in these events and meetings will enable knowledge exchange with relevant communities, projects, and initiatives, gather up-to-date information regarding the latest news on DC Solutions and will foster networking. The type of meeting will vary according to the profile and expertise of the partner involved. For instance, industrial-related partners may attend workshops, information days, and internal and external client meetings, while research-related partners will target more scientific congresses and meetings.

In all cases, all project partners are expected to inform the Coordination Team through e-mail shift2dc.coordination@inesc-id.pt, at least two weeks in advance (see Section 4.54.5 for additional guidelines).

By M6, the Shift2DC consortium had already been involved in several events:

- **12-13, December 2023:** Shift2DC Kick-off Meeting at Instituto Superior Técnico gathering members from all partner Institutions from 13 different European countries, online and remotely, and with the online presence of the Project Officer (PO).
- **12-15, March 2024:** Mostra Convegno Expocomfort in Milan – EHPA promoted the project in the Association's booth at the event.
- **03 April 2024:** Visit to Demo site and meeting between Portuguese Partners in Funchal, Madeira (Portugal).
- **9-10, April 2024:** Bridge General Assembly in Brussels with the participation of Hugo Morais (INESC ID).
- **22 April 2024:** European Heat Pump Association (EHPA) Meeting between Shift2DC partners and EHPA Associates to present new DC Solutions.
- **15 May 2024:** Participation in the JRP DC Grids final workshop (Netherlands). Participant: Hugo Morais (INESC ID).

The above-mentioned actions will guarantee that the project results will be disseminated and exploited, e.g., communicated, transferred towards target stakeholders. To evaluate the impact of the project's dissemination

activities, the project consortium has a set of specific metrics or KPIs to monitor its achievements effectively (Table 7).

4.3 Organization of Workshops/Events

Shift2DC partners will organize at least four workshops, one per demonstration site. The main goal of these workshops is to inform about Shift2DC solutions, tools, methodologies and increase collaboration with other initiatives presented in Section 5.

The demonstration site events will target all group audiences. Since the demonstration activities will only start at M13, these events are expected to occur between the second and third year of the project.

These events will increase collaboration with other initiatives, projects, and programs and allow the exchange of research, information, and dissemination.

4.4 Synergies with Peer Projects

Shift2DC partners have committed to promoting liaisons and joint activities with other European research projects, communities, and initiatives. Those synergies will target mainly the Scientific communities and energy-related industry mainly system operators and aggregators.

Shift2DC has also recently joined the BRIDGE initiative and participated in the 2024 Bridge General Assembly that took place in Brussels on April 9th and 10th, represented by the Project Coordinator at INESC ID Hugo Morais. BRIDGE is structured over 4 specific work groups (WG): regulation, business models, data management and customer engagement, and Shift2DC had assigned expert partners to join each WG.

Shift2DC will also participate in events promoting network and synergies with other European projects such as ENLIT Networking events. The 2024 ENLIT Forum will take place in Milan between October 22 and 24 and Shift2DC is assessing its participation.

4.5 Guidelines on Consortium Participation in Dissemination Activities

To maintain an up-to-date record of all activities it is required that the partners follow specific guidelines. Those are listed below.

Participation in Events, Scientific meetings, Congresses, and Workshops:

- A minimum of two weeks before the activity, the partners should send an e-mail to the Coordination Team using shift2dc.coordination@inesc-id.pt with the following details about the activity: type of activity, date, title, audience, and the role of the partner. This prior notice is required for the Project Coordination Team to advertise the activity on time on social media and the website.
- Additionally, participants are also encouraged to share the activity among the consortium (shift2dc.consortium@inesc-id.pt) and stakeholders, to increase network opportunities with project partners and stakeholders.

- During or right after the activity, the partner should create a folder in the Shift2DC internal SharePoint under “WP 6 – Events” (alternatively they can send the information to the coordination mailing list), fill in the template “News and Events Submission form” with relevant information about their participation, and upload photos of their participation, abstract, article or poster presented and/or presentation.

Publication of Scientific Publications

- All partners should inform the Shift2DC Coordination Team (shift2dc.coordination@inesc-id.pt) about all submitted and accepted publications – this information is collected for the Shift2DC publication database (management record) and will be shared on the project website and social media.
- All publications, including scientific articles, should include the following disclaimer (under the acknowledgement section): *“This work received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101056765. Views and opinions expressed in this document are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”*

5 Evaluation and Monitoring of D&C Activities

To evaluate the impact of the project’s dissemination activities, the Shift2DC consortium has established, during proposal preparation, a specific set of metrics to monitor its achievements effectively. The KPIs have been revised and are presented in Table 6 and Table 7. The KPIs will be monitored throughout the whole project, monthly, to help evaluate project progress and to develop interim and annual reports.

Table 6 - Shift2DC Communication KPIs

Channel	KPI	M6	Targets	Expected Impact
Website	Number of unique visitors	0	2 000	Main online information channel; Communication of project news, events & results; Liaisons with other initiatives, projects, working groups; Increased awareness. Drive engagement with the project.
	Number of references to the project on search engines	0	25	
Social media X/Twitter account	Number of accumulative followers	41	200	Increased visibility to stakeholders active in social media; Attainment of interest of stakeholders;
Social Media LinkedIn account	Number of accumulative followers	581	200	Direct communication with followers. Drive engagement with the project
Publications in general media	Number of articles in magazines, newspapers	19	2	Increased project visibility and the impact on the society.
Dissemination Kit	Number of project presentations	1	1	Communication of project news, events & results; Increased awareness. Unique branding and visual identity of the project; Improves communication of results and information provision during events.
	Number of project banners	1	1	
	Number of videos	0	6	
	Number of press releases	1	2	
	Number of project factsheets/ brochures	1	2	
	Number of project posters	0	2	
	Number of Newsletters	0	6	

Table 7 - Shift2DC Dissemination KPIs

KPI	M6	Targets	Targeted individuals	Comments
Number of attended events	4	20	Gathering ideas and exchanging knowledge about latest DC system news	Brochure, leaflets, poster, project presentation
Number of events where the project has been presented	4	5		
Number of workshops organized	0	4	Inform about Shift2DC solutions, tools, methodologies. Increase collaboration with other initiatives and dissemination.	Brochure, leaflets, poster, project presentation
Average number of attendees per workshop	0	20		
Number of DEMO events	0	4		
Number of scientific publications	0	21	Inform about the project outcomes and benefits. Validation of the project	Conferences, scientific press media
Number of articles in specialized magazines/journals	0	3	Inform about project outcomes and benefits	Industry press, media, conferences
Panel discussions	0	2	Promotion of the project's results and achievements	Conferences
Number of scientific dissemination material	2	3	Communication of project results and achievements, new synergies, and collaborations	Posters, brochure, leaflets, roll-ups

6 Conclusions

This deliverable provided an initial plan for the communication and dissemination activities to be developed under the Shift2DC project. These activities are key to maximize the impact of the project and therefore, it was first important to guarantee that they were built upon a solid image, identity, and based on well-structured online presence.

Therefore, between months 2 and 6 the focus of the WP6 was to build a strong visual and brand identity to support all D&C activities, ranging from the project online presence (website, social media) to promotional materials or participation in events. The result of these efforts was a clearly recognizable logo and brand image that will enhance Shift2DC initiatives throughout the project lifespan.

The launch of the Social Media accounts was also an important milestone, key to raising project awareness, visibility, and engagement. For the next few months, the coordination team will keep on working to increase the numbers of followers on X/Twitter and LinkedIn, which already had a significant number of followers by month 6 (581 followers). Specific campaigns will also be planned to help us grow and engage with the project audiences.

The development of the Shift2DC website was also one of the main endeavours of this first semester and will be serve as the project primary online communication channel, requiring a well-thought structure and relevant contents.

Templates for several uses have also been developed and some dissemination activities have already been planned and initiated (a scientific article is in preparation, a conference paper is planned for an international conference, four events attended and three already under evaluation).

Throughout the deliverable, the attention is drawn to consortium partners' important role in supporting these activities. Shift2DC consortium contains multidisciplinary entities, with specific expertise and an established network, which can help us reach many stakeholders. Thus, the active participation of the partners in this strategic plan is crucial to increase the impact of Shift2DC in industry, academia, authorities, and society.

This deliverable is a live document, and it will be updated at M24, or earlier if changes are applied. Furthermore, this document will also be complemented by a complete Innovation and Exploitation Plan (D5.1) to be submitted at M12 and updated at M36 (D5.2).

7 References

- [1] European Commission, "Horizon Europe (HORIZON) Programme Guide." May 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
- [2] European Commission, "EU Grants. AGA- Annotated Model Grant Agreement. Eu Funding Programmes 2021-2027." May 01, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

ANNEX I

Standard Style Guidelines

To ensure the readability of the logo, its elements were designed with specific margins and spacing that must be maintained (ANNEX I – Figure 1). The smallest size the logo can be is 3 cm high in the vertical format and 1 cm long in the horizontal format (ANNEX I – Figure 2).

Structure

ANNEX I - Figure 1 – Shift2DC logo with margins and spacing

Dimensions

ANNEX I - Figure 2 – Shift2DC logo size

The logo should never be changed, stretched, or distorted. ANNEX I – Figure 3 shows examples of the incorrect use of the Shift2DC logo.

Dont's

ANNEX I - Figure 3 – Don'ts for Shift2DC Logo

The Shift2DC main font is Arial for text and titles, to be used in dissemination materials, PPT presentations, newsletters, and website. Examples of the lettering, type, and size available to use are shown in ANNEX I - Figure 4.

Typography

for documents

Arial

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Ii Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp
 Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
 0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
 ~ ! @ # \$ % & / | \ () []

Regular **A B C 1 9**
 Regular Italic **A B C 1 9**
 Bold **A B C 1 9**
 Bold Italic **A B C 1 9**

ANNEX I - Figure 4 – Shift2DC main font, Arial

In official documents, such as deliverables, and internal and mid-term reports, the font used is Arial, size 11 for body text, 16 for titles, 14 for subtitles and 12 for sub-subtitles.

The materials produced for the Shift2DC project (templates, banners, flyers, website) contain key graphic elements that reflect the vision and ideas of the project. Those elements are represented in ANNEX I - Figure 5

and include charging stations, cars, wind power, garage, houses, photovoltaic panels, trees, benches and bicycles.

ANNEX I - Figure 5 – Graphic elements presented in the Shift2DC project

ANNEX II

The power point template is presented bellow in Annex II - Figure 1.

Annex II - Figure 1 – Shift2DC PPT Template

ANNEX III

News Title	Date	News Media
Horizon Europe SHIFT2DC project secures over €11m to advance green energy solutions	10/01/2024	Innovation News Network
Europe Paves the Way for a Sustainable Future: The Sustronics and SHIFT2DC Initiatives	10/01/2024	BNN Breaking
SHIFT2DC Kick-Off Meeting	10/01/2024	ITI LarsYs
Projeto europeu tem mais de 11M€ para desenvolver soluções de energia mais sustentáveis e inteligentes	12/01/2024	Ambiente Magazine
Projeto europeu desenvolve soluções de energia mais sustentáveis e inteligentes	16/01/2024	Indústria e Ambiente
SHIFT2DC EU Project kicks off in Lisbon	16/01/2024	EHPA
Arranca el proyecto SHIFT2DC para crear soluciones de corriente continua más inteligentes	18/01/2024	SMART GRIDS INFO
SHIFT2DC Kick-Off Meeting in Lisbon (in ENG)	18/01/2024	
SHIFT2DC: rivoluzione energetica in Europa con l'innovativo uso della corrente continua	18/01/2024	ExpoClima
Portos da Madeira integram projeto de investigação que recebeu financiamento de 11 milhões de euros	23/01/2024	dnóticias
Portos da Madeira integram projeto de investigação europeu de 11 milhões de euros	23/01/2024	JM Madeira
PROJETO EUROPEU SHIFT2DC TEM MAIS DE 11M€ PARA DESENVOLVER SOLUÇÕES DE ENERGIA MAIS SUSTENTÁVEIS E INTELIGENTES	23/01/2024	O Electricista
PORTS OF MADEIRA ARE PART OF A RESEARCH PROJECT THAT RECEIVED FUNDING OF 11 MILLION EUROS	23/01/2024	Madeira Island News
Porto do Funchal integra projeto de investigação europeu para criar infraestruturas eficientes e sustentáveis	23/01/2024	Água & Ambiente
Porto do Funchal integra projeto europeu para criação de infraestruturas sustentáveis	23/01/2024	RTP Madeira
APRAM integra projeto europeu de 11 milhões de euros para criar infraestruturas de energia mais inteligentes	23/01/2024	Jornal Económico
Porto do Funchal integra projeto europeu para criação de infraestruturas sustentáveis	23/01/2024	Green Savers
Ports of Madeira are part of a research project that received funding of 11 million euros	23/01/2024	Aicep Portugal Global
Madeira Ports Part of 11 Million Euro Research Project	25/01/2024	Madeira Weekly

Annex III - Figure 1 - Published News (19) are presented bellow in.